

MODERN METHODS OF INFORMATION PRESENTATION IN TELEVISION NEWS BROADCASTING

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Abstract. *This article examines contemporary methods of presenting news media products on television. A comparative analysis of news programs on Uzbek and Russian television reveals new approaches to traditional methods of delivering information to audiences, news promotion technologies on modern television, and methods for increasing viewer interest in channel-produced news programs through interaction with new media. The article also demonstrates the transformation of headlines, advertisements, and advertising tactics in television news products in the context of digitalization.*

Keywords: *television news broadcasting; information presentation; infotainment; hard news; soft news; news promotion; digitalization.*

Introduction. It is generally acknowledged that among the vast stream of information about life on our planet, news undoubtedly ranks first in importance. It is news that, above all, paints a constantly changing socio-political, economic, social, and cultural picture of the world, representing the most vital information for the functioning of society. Television undoubtedly dominates the rapid delivery of information to people around the world, ignoring borders and distances, bringing news to every home. Within the mass media system, television has established itself as the most convenient, accessible, regular, and vibrant news broadcasting channel. News is broadcast on TV by major stations for most of the day, creating not only a panorama of current events but also forming the basis of the daily program, figuratively speaking, its "skeleton." The significance of news for the audience, its volume, and the various forms of delivery determine the overall organization of a TV channel's information broadcasting.

On television, news is typically organized into news programs, which in television journalism theory are often referred to as "newscasts," "news bulletins," or "informational releases." They are not something static in form; the volume of their broadcasts and, naturally, the approaches to covering events, the level of objectivity, the nature of presentation, and the degree of dependence of television organizations on the political system of society change. Moreover, as the most mobile and significant, news broadcasts not only reflect the station's information policy but also influence other programs.

It has long been established that study of the experience of domestic and foreign television stations and channels in producing news programs, in our opinion, will not only allow us to identify patterns in the field of news broadcasting, but also answer questions concerning vital areas of modern domestic television journalism and develop effective means of improving the activities of television stations and television channels as a whole.

Review of the literature on the topic. In the process of researching the issue of forms and methods of presenting news information on television, it was found that very few works

devoted to this problem are available. Scientific thought is mainly focused on modern trends in the development of television broadcasting, its structural features, television genres, etc. It is enough to recall the works of A.S. Vartanov [3], V.V. Zvereva [7], K.P. Kovalev-Sluchevsky [10], G.V. Kuznetsov [11], P.I. Misyulya [13], S.A. Muratov [14] and others, devoted to the theory and practice of television in general.

The works of E. Fichtelius [20], V.L. Tsvik [21] were devoted to certain aspects of information television broadcasting.

Uzbek researchers A. Karimov [9], I. Rakhmatullaeva [18], P. Allambergenova [1], and others have made significant contributions to identifying the specific features of national television broadcasting.

Analysis of Russian television channels' experience in delivering news to viewers has been undertaken over the years by scholars E. Nikolskaya and M. Makeenko [15], L. Kostina [12], D. Bykov [2], E. Sheykhova, P. Ibragimova [23], and others. In their research, they attempted to define the types of information presentation in news programs from the perspective of a specific empirical approach: from the perspective of infotainment, from the standpoint of the characteristics of individual expressive screen media, and based on the technical capabilities of television studios.

Nevertheless, in the context of rapidly developing scientific and technological progress and an expanding range of technologies, the study of new formats for information presentation in modern television news programs within a comprehensive and systemic paradigm seems particularly relevant.

Research methodology. To identify general principles of news construction and the most effective ways to compose news reports, a method for analyzing information delivery methods at the textual level was used. As part of the conceptual content analysis, a text sentiment analysis was also applied, determining whether the news was positive, negative, or neutral.

The synthesis method allowed us to identify the visual characteristics of news stories included in the structure of news programs and to identify the most characteristic video and audio components of news information, such as introductions, stand-up comedy, voiceover, and others.

The comparative method was particularly important, reflecting not only the comparative analysis of foreign and Uzbek television channels but also the comparison of the on-screen language of the broadcasting structures under study and the methods used by different journalists to influence audiences.

Main Part.

The very nature of television and its impact on audiences are the subject of close attention from sociologists, politicians, philologists, psychologists, and others. This is not simply a tribute to television's popularity, but, above all, a manifestation of concern for the future of society, given the enormous role television plays in modern culture and social life. The speed of information transmission, the broad range of topics, the virtually unlimited geographical reach of on-the-spot broadcasts, the virtual presence effect, and the convenience of home viewing—the entire set of characteristic and distinctive features of television, as is well known, have ensured it has the largest audience in the early 21st century.

The role of news broadcasts in the structure of television production is steadily increasing. And as the renowned television journalism researcher A.S. Vartanov rightly noted, "a block of proprietary news programs is the most essential element that allows one to 'distinguish a reputable company from one that airs old films, liberally interspersed with commercials'" [3; 46].

There is widespread agreement that in the modern world, constantly receiving information from various spheres of life—economic, political, social, and cultural—has become the norm. Hence, news programs are the anchor points of any television company's broadcast schedule, with all other programs located in the intervals between news bulletins [6; 39].

"The calling card of any channel is information. It is the first injection the channel gives to a person waking up. It is what the channel sends off to sleep with; it is the energy that charges viewers with initiative or dampens it. And finding your own twists in the presentation of information is fundamentally important." This is the opinion of one of the most renowned organizers of Russian television broadcasting, O. M. Poptsov [16; 104].

News delivery today is influenced by:

- competition between television companies themselves;
- the presence of news from other media outlets;
- the programming focus of television stations, "format" requirements;
- the forced or deliberate combination of local and international news, important and entertaining, etc. [20; 23].

Modern television news journalism has a variety of forms and methods. Historically established methods of presenting operational materials, such as "infotainment," "event action," "build-up," "finishing," "headline," "hard news," "soft news," and others, are now being transformed into something entirely new.

Television news journalism today is challenging because it lacks rigid standards for news delivery, and the stories of many news programs are quite open-ended and sometimes extend beyond the scope of conventional reporting. But this places even greater responsibility on journalists, as new news reporting techniques require careful and competent use.

In news broadcasting, a distinction is made between "hard" and "soft" reporting.

"Hard" reporting. This involves clear answers to the classic questions "Who? What? Where? When? Why? How?" and a text structured like an "inverted pyramid." The journalist places the most important information in the headline, with the remaining details included throughout the text. With this format, the headline is uncluttered with secondary details and unnecessary details, so as not to distract from the main content. For example, the headline of one of the stories on the news program "Vakt" reads: "Uzbek chess player Zhavokhir Sindarov defeated his Indian opponent Rameshbabu Pragnanandhaa in the third round of the Candidates Tournament in Peira, Cyprus" [Poytaxt issue dated April 14, 2026]. The headline appears to be accurate and precise. But in reality, this headline contains virtually all the information about the event, and it is unclear why the viewer would continue watching the news program if they have already learned the most important information. Experts believe that a headline should, first and foremost, "lure" the viewer in, enticing them to watch not only the current news item, but ideally, the entire broadcast [5; 175-176]. In our opinion, a headline should contain some intrigue. For example, the headline of one of the stories featured in the April issue of "Vesti" reads as follows: "'Apartment Buildings Collapsed': Consequences of Israeli Strikes in Lebanon" [Vesti issue on the Rossiya 1 channel, April 29, 2026]. Naturally, such a headline will intrigue the viewer and encourage them to stay in front of the television. It should be especially emphasized that news headlines should not distort reality and should be accurate.

In television broadcasting, there are situations when something extraordinary happens and a news program on a particular channel reports it for the first time. A headline like "flash" should literally explode on the air. Even if it captures the essence of the event, the audience's attention, as

we see it, will still be riveted to the broadcast of a given television studio or channel. Here's an example: "A fire broke out at the Beshkurgan market near the Hippodrome" [Poytaxt broadcast on the Toshkent channel, April 5, 2026]. As we can see, the essence of the incident has been conveyed to the listener. But the questions—what kind of fire, what caused it, and what the consequences—remain—remain, meaning attention is riveted to the message, and the viewer will in any case await details.

"Soft" information. Foreign researchers call this method of information "human touch" [19; 103]. Domestic television broadcasters call it "bows."

It is important to note that the "hard" news format, which primarily features highly timely announcements, "soft" news is less timely, or rather, timeliness is less important. Touches and details highlight the unusual and entertaining, introducing a touch of intrigue. The soft news format allows for a closer look at the facts, shifting attention from the summary to the circumstances, and highlighting interesting details. Therefore, the news structure changes; the "inverted pyramid" principle of composition is unsuitable. The headline and introduction are constructed with viewer interest in mind; the essence is not immediately presented, but the most interesting part is delayed until the second or even third paragraph. Interest builds until the climax.

Journalists working in the soft news style on television are especially attentive to "visual reinforcements" – and these often prove truly valuable creative insights. For example, in one of the episodes of the Vesti program from March 6, 2025, in a selection of stories for International Women's Day, the correspondent, talking about men's preparations for this holiday, found unusual congratulations from Russians: the word "mama" laid out at the entrance to an apartment building using cars, a flower bed in the capital's park with an original frame "We cannot live in this world without women" [Episode "Vesti" of the channel "Russia 1" from 06.03.2025.], etc. And in the episode of the program "Poytaxt", also timed to coincide with a beautiful spring date, correspondent Sanobar Umarova managed to film an interesting story about the passion of our compatriots for flowers, simultaneously revealing the secret of the so-called "flower" flights [Episode "Poytaxt" of the channel "Toshkent" from 07.03.2024.].

When working on a television report, a journalist chooses the format of presentation that best suits the facts. Soft news is used when it's necessary to engage the listener, shifting the emphasis from the results to the circumstances. The circumstances of an event, or certain details surrounding the event, can be more interesting than the outcome. Many soft news are funny, entertaining, and add a touch of excitement to the news. For example: "There are still girls in Russia who...can stop a galloping horse and enter a burning hut." A case in Argentina is an example of this. A Russian woman not only managed to get her phone back from robbers but also helped catch an entire gang of thieves in the area. In the video, we see how a girl on a bicycle managed not only to grab hold of a robber, but also to knock him off his motorcycle and hold him until backup arrived [News episode of the Moscow 24 channel, November 17, 2025].

It is universally recognised that over the past decade, television broadcasting has seen a shift toward a so-called "human" approach to news, where events are depicted and illustrated, rather than simply dryly reported. Many researchers believe that audiences, especially young people, don't want to simply "listen" to the news, as they can get information from other sources, such as radio and the internet. People want to hear a "story about current events." Many Russians, in a survey conducted by Mediascope, responded that a "personalized presentation of news messages" is very important to them, and that they are "tired of 'wooden' boys on the air" [24].

In this regard, it is important to consider that small digression is necessary. The personalized way news is presented, in the minds of many of us, contradicts the fundamental principles that have been ingrained in Russian journalism for many years: news is just news, and nothing personal, no judgments, is allowed. But "humanizing" information doesn't mean evaluating it. It means personifying it—intoning it, emphasizing it, presenting it in a "human" way. As an example, consider a segment from the "Vesti" program about the so-called "advertising heralds," or simply "barkers," of Moscow. The segment, running 3 minutes and 12 seconds, tells the story of employees of outerwear, bakery, confectionery, and cosmetics stores whose loudspeakers disturb nearby residents. In particular, interviews were provided with a woman whose mother-in-law is paralyzed and with the mother of a four-year-old girl, who complained that loud noises had caused them to forget about rest, and that neither the patient nor the small child could fall asleep during the day [Vesti broadcast on the Rossiya 1 channel, February 9, 2025].

This example clearly demonstrates the type of "humanized news," i.e., news that presents an event or phenomenon through the prism of human stories.

It is regrettable that in the context of domestic television broadcasting, it is too early to talk about this; most journalists on Uzbek television news programs have a surprising and all-consuming passion for so-called "officialdom," the presentation of information within strictly defined frameworks.

The overabundance of official announcements on air only serves to alienate modern audiences. However, the older portion of listeners, accustomed to this particular manner of news delivery throughout their lives, still perceive official reports quite calmly, paying little attention to them. Nevertheless, the pace of life itself dictates different forms and methods of presenting news.

Journalistic material of any length requires truly creative work, a search for form, and a refinement of content. Russian researcher L. A. Vasilyeva urges: "Try to find new forms of news presentation, play with information, package it beautifully, make it sparkle with all the facets of an event..." [4; 56].

As this study has shown, methods of presenting information—"infotainment," "finishing," "event action," headline, and promotions—contribute new color to news programs and the stories they contain.

Infotainment "emerged as an acronym combining two words: information and entertainment, and expresses producers' desire to present news in the form of entertaining programs or with a touch of entertainment" [8]. The concept of "infotainment" implies adding vibrancy to a program presenting the events of the day or week, focusing on entertainment. Today, it's especially important for broadcasters to keep audiences glued to their televisions, and in this context, "interestingness" is becoming the primary criterion for news. Infotainment presupposes a dramatic narrative with a premise, development, climax, resolution, and recognizable characters. It is characterized by an emphasis on spectacle, brevity, and dynamism, clip-like editing, a high tempo, and rapid image changes.

In television news journalism, "infotainment" refers to a persistent and highly perceptible trend toward a gradual shift in the function of news: from informing to entertaining the audience. Numerous studies using television news show a significant shift toward celebrity news, entertainment, scandals, and crimes involving famous people, as well as lifestyle news [25]. Such "news-as-entertainment" helps to alleviate the tension of some newscasts, sweetening the news pill of the broadcast day. Here are some examples of news stories created in the infotainment format:

– “A macaque baby named Punch, a resident of the Japanese zoo in Ichikawa, has not only become famous thanks to a viral video featuring a stuffed orangutan, but has also helped the zoo significantly increase visitor numbers from 20,000 to 90,000. Born in July 2025, the baby was abandoned by its mother, and zoo staff were forced to raise it themselves. During this period, the baby became attached to the stuffed orangutan, which effectively became its mother.

Today, Punch is receiving messages and gifts from all over the world. The story of the Japanese macaque baby has become an example of how touching moments in the lives of animals can unite people around the world – and literally change the fate of an entire zoo” [Sevimli channel's "Zamon" episode, April 10, 2026].

"A first-grader's mother has declared war on school extortion." This was the headline of a news report on the Vesti program. The report, broadcast by a Vesti correspondent in the Sverdlovsk region, featured Maria Korchina, a 34-year-old resident of Alapaevsk who refused to donate to the school fund. In an interview with the correspondent, the woman revealed that she had been asked to pay 6,500 rubles for school repairs. But the most intriguing part came at the end of the report, when the woman learned that her son hadn't even been enrolled in school yet [Vesti broadcast on the Rossiya 1 channel, September 4, 2024].

Modern news programs also often use infotainment as a re-enactment of the news. L.A. Vasilyeva believes that this method of presenting information allows for a variety of perspectives and, in its broad creative potential, is similar to a play-acting performance [4:81]. In particular, the March 3, 2025, news broadcast of the Vesti. Duty Station channel featured a report on a traffic accident caused by singer Alexander Buinov. The news of the singer hitting a kindergarten teacher at a crosswalk had already been part of the program on February 28 of last year. In the March broadcast, the correspondent presented the incident from the perspective of a reconstruction of the event, and through certain details (specially selected camera angles, special effects), the story was given a certain spectacle and staged feel [Vesti. [The "Duty Section" segment of the Rossiya 1 channel, March 3, 2025.]

It should be especially noted that television news programs have recently increasingly featured instances of so-called politicized infotainment, where the subjects are no longer show business personalities, but well-known politicians and prominent figures. As an example, we cite a segment from the Russian program "Vesti," which aired in April of this year.

"Correspondent: During a speech at the White House, King Charles III of Great Britain joked about the burning of the building by the British in 1814, calling it "a small attempt at development" and comparing it to the current renovation of the East Wing, initiated by US President Donald Trump.

This refers to the demolition of the East Wing of the White House to build a ballroom. According to the British king, US President Donald Trump decided on the changes after his visit to Windsor Castle last year. As the Daily Mail reported the day before, Trump broke protocol during his visit by patting Charles III on the shoulder. Body language expert Judy James noted that the gesture could have been politically motivated. In her opinion, (quote), "the touch was Trump's first genuine gesture of active, 'special' friendship." [Vesti broadcast on Rossiya 1, April 29, 2026.]

Another news delivery method worth focusing on is finishing. It's a journalistic technique that capitalizes on the resonance of a media report, revisiting one or more aspects of a situation, but from a new, unexpected perspective. On television, a modification of this method is manifested in the so-called "spinning" of a news story. This means enhancing the value of a particular

message. Experience in news broadcasting shows that it's crucial not only to find the news itself, but also to be able to promote it, generating excitement and public agitation. This will enhance its impact, achieve its goal, and boost the channel's ratings.

Comparing finishing with infotainment, the latter makes the news more prominent, expanding its informational and newsworthy scope, while finishing allows for a deeper dive into the situation. A television journalist is like an oil producer, developing oil reservoir after reservoir. After all, journalism is not an art whose inherent property is fiction. It is also more complex because, unlike art, the truth of life coincides with the truth of fact.

Modern television news journalism is not simply about reporting current events, but the ability to work with facts, develop the information received, and present it in a way that is memorable to viewers. In this context, news promotion is effective.

It should be noted that just a few years ago, it was believed that news promotion was unnecessary, since viewers knew when it would air. Today, audiovisual media professionals understand that promotion is an excellent means of increasing the ratings of news broadcasts.

Let's analyze the most effective types of promotion for television news products.

Image promotion is how a television channel wants viewers to perceive it. The editorial staff strives to convey an image, an impression of how the news program is compiled. Therefore, the news program must correspond to this image and reinforce it with daily practice. If a TV channel has the opportunity to promote a news program, it should choose a time slot that will attract as many viewers as possible. If the news program airs during evening prime time, it makes sense to schedule the promo before the news, as is done on the country's leading television channels. Another possible location is morning prime time. When editing such a promotion, excerpts from field reports and studio-recorded segments are typically used.

The next type of news promotion is a thematic promo. Typically, this is an advertisement for a story—one or more—that will be broadcast during the news program, such as a special report. Such an advertisement typically includes a highlight video clip from the report to be aired during the news program. Experts recommend placing such a story at the end of the program so that viewers can watch other news while waiting for it [17; 92].

The third type of promotion is a high-quality one. This type of promotion is usually included after the news broadcast. This could be a reminder for viewers or a summary. For example, a TV channel's news service announces that it is switching to a different operating mode or has changed its broadcast schedule, and news will be broadcast at a different time. One way to create a high-quality promotion is to leverage the opinions of the target audience, city residents, and passersby on the street. Their authoritative opinion on the quality of the news programs will convince others more than any words from the presenters.

Besides on-air news promotion, there are many other ways to attract attention to news broadcasts. These include badges, T-shirts with slogans, stickers, and keychains with the logo and phone number of the television company or its news service. These are given to interviewees, for example.

Another promising area of television news reporting is campaigns. These are actions taken to achieve a specific goal. In television journalism, campaigns typically have a humanitarian focus. Their goal, like the goal of all journalism, is to help people. Television campaigns have multiple stages. Typically, they consist of:

- 1) announcement of the start of the campaign (the launch);
- 2) sponsorship promotion (intermediate stage);
- 3) summing up.

It is becoming increasingly clear that example of a campaign in television news programs is the "Dobro" campaign on Channel One. This is a joint campaign by Channel One and the Russian Foundation for Dissemination of Good. It is periodically featured on the "Vremya" news program, and proceeds from viewers go toward the treatment of seriously ill children [26]. Similar campaigns are also periodically organized by regional Russian television channels. For example, "Vesti. Novosibirsk" broadcast on April 30 of this year featured a story about 8-year-old Timofey, who suffers from cerebral palsy and needs help [27]. Unfortunately, such campaigns are not held on national television channels in Uzbekistan.

Among the effective forms of news presentation, the clip headline is noteworthy. In television news broadcasting, headlines for all news stories are typically constructed according to traditional press models (narrative headline-message, headline-quote, headline-summary, compound headlines, appeal, appeal, exclamation, headline with "continuation," with a colon, playful headline, etc.). A clip-based headline is a form of emphasis, achieved through any means: underlining, increasing the size, changing the font of a keyword, intonation, etc. For example, the headlines of the "Vesti" news program sometimes take the form of clip-based headlines: "Five-Star" Grandma ["Vesti. Novosibirsk" from April 24, 2026], "Drone Hunting Over the Dnieper," "Euro-Tranche for Ukraine: Reforms Under Pressure" ["Vesti" from April 29, 2026], etc.

The so-called "packaging" of a news broadcast plays a significant role in the presentation of news. "Packaging" is everything that presents the news program to the viewer. This concept includes the logo, news intro, color scheme, studio design, computer graphics, etc.

The logo of the Russian program has remained unchanged for several years: the word "Vesti" in pale blue on a bright blue background. The news sign and studio design have undergone a makeover: the bright blue colors that have dominated the program's design for many years have given way to a new color scheme—soft, sky-blue and blue tones. The sign perfectly harmonizes with the studio's color scheme. The set has become more modern: the steel frames of the desks behind which the anchors of the news program "Vesti" sit represent the continuous conveyor of information flowing into the studio, and the shimmering blue "panorama" in the lower right corner of the studio image attests to the constant flow of information. In contrast to the steel color of the "waist" desk behind which the anchor sits, the logo, the sign, and the studio's overall understated design emphasize the seriousness and thoroughness of the program.

The Uzbek program "Poytaxt" has also undergone a design overhaul. The studio's gray tones have been replaced by a calming blue. This color scheme is a welcome change. The combination of various shades of blue creates a positive atmosphere, not overwhelming or tiring, but invigorating and relaxing. Shades of light blue and blue symbolize inner strength and harmony. The freshness of these colors, combined with their calming influence, makes them desirable, as they relieve stress and promote a calmer perception of the information being conveyed. A contemporary style is also evident here: the pedestal behind which the presenters sit is made of plastic in the same color as the studio's decor, its irregular shape creating a sense of diversity and multifacetedness.

It's worth noting that both news programs make minimal use of infographics, such as maps, diagrams, or charts. The active use of infographics is more typical of Western European TV channels such as Euronews, France 24, Sky News, and others. Infographics are also common on the Uzbek TV channel UzReport.

The news programs "Poytaxt" and "Vesti" also share the use of titles, interludes, and announcements (spiegels). Both programs begin with spiegels—announcements of the program's

contents. Spiegels use a condensed presentation of the main points of the stories, outlining the timeframe of the event and its main characters. The purpose of spiegels is to facilitate comprehension "by fragmenting information and drawing viewers' attention to the program" [13;173].

The intro to "Poytaxt" is a musical background with a rhythmic, rapid beat. The stories are announced by the program's correspondents at a fast tempo, with restrained but emotional voiceovers. The presentation of information on the program "Poytaxt" is strict and somewhat formal. Stand-up comedy is practically nonexistent.

For viewers of the program "Vesti," news is presented in a more personalized, emotional, but unbiased manner. Brief, precise summaries and textual "connections" between stories make the news program on the Rossiya-1 channel not only more digestible but also more comfortable for the viewer.

Personification can also be considered a distinctive feature of modern television news programs. In this regard, the "Vesti" news service, where the technique of personification has been further developed, is an advantage.

The concept of news personification is considered not only in terms of its content, where journalistic materials focus on people, their feelings, fates, and experiences, but also in terms of the presentation and form of the information materials. In this sense, stand-up comedy, as well as the constant, persistent "advertising" of its own reporters, can be considered formal signs of personification.

A typical example of this technique on the evening program "Vesti" is the newscast previews (spiegels), which feature correspondents, as well as the numerous stand-up routines that are given considerable time in news segments.

Regular viewers of "Vesti" know the reporters by sight, recognize their voices, and even their creative style. The work of journalists on the program "Poytaxt," unfortunately, is less individualized.

We believe that this method of personalization has a positive impact on audience trust in the source of information, since by trusting a specific reporter, a personalized source, the audience is more interested in the information itself.

Experts note that the unity of a TV station's visual image is achieved through the correct combination of graphic techniques, digital video effects, and electronic captions throughout each broadcast day [14;112]. One effective way to harmoniously combine all of these elements is to create a distinctive graphic "backdrop" for news programs. For example, in the "Vesti" program, the backdrop features the most striking sections of the story, the introduction to which is spoken by the presenter. Since the graphics are consistent with the overall image of the Rossiya-1 channel, they effectively highlight the presenter's text, illustrate it, and attract the attention of those viewers who were only half-watching the program. Seeing a successful visual image on the backdrop, they are likely to approach the television and turn up the volume or do the same on the remote control. A well-designed graphic design for the "Vesti" news program not only adds dimension to the studio set but also emphasizes the fact that news is the most important part of the channel's broadcast.

In the news program "Poytaxt," previews of upcoming stories are presented in a multidimensional image of rapidly changing cubes containing clips of the most interesting segments of the broadcast. Viewers associate the receding corridor of broadcast events with an

endless stream of news reports, directing our attention deeper into the events and phenomena being covered.

Therefore, the increasing multichannel nature of modern television and the competition between channels inevitably impacted news—the core of virtually any television company. Stylistic unity, efficiency, and a commitment to comprehensive and objective coverage—all of these have become the hallmarks of the news programs "Poytaxt" and "Vesti," defining their niche positions in the TV news space. Unlike many modern news programs, such as "Segodnya" (NTV) and "Vestnik" (TNT), both programs do not focus on human tragedy. Their principle of news ranking is to give the audience an objective understanding of current events in the world and the country.

Furthermore, the creators of the programs "Poytaxt" and "Vesti" avoid excessive dramatization. They strictly adhere to the principle of separating facts from opinions. No "yellow press" was observed in the programs we analyzed. Both programs rely on the competence of their presenters, correspondents, and reporters.

Conclusion. Thus, it can be concluded that the methods of presenting information in modern news broadcasting have changed: they have become more original, engaging, and sometimes entertaining. The way news is presented has also evolved: for example, reports have begun to emphasize details of interest to viewers. Many television channels are forced to shift the emphasis of their news programs from political and official information to coverage of pressing social issues, scandalous and bizarre stories, cultural events, and the like.

It cannot be overlooked that the study showed, unlike foreign television companies, Uzbek television news programs do not veer sharply toward entertainment; they are more carefully crafted and balanced.

It should be pointed out that many television channels employ news delivery techniques such as "infotainment," "event action," "finishing," "headline"-type events, "hard news," "soft news," and others. Many TV news programs emphasize spectacle, clip-like plots, concise and dynamic presentation, complex editing, high tempo, and rapid image changes.

The plots of many news programs are quite open-ended and sometimes extend beyond the scope of standard information. Such news delivery techniques require careful and competent use by television journalists.

For increasing viewer attention to the news, news producers have begun to employ marketing specialists who are developing new concepts for presenting information using simplified stories, "light" topics, rich visuals, and increased emotionality in the delivery of materials.

In light of the above, it seems advisable to:

- prioritize the quality of news releases over quantity;
- organize news releases based on audience needs, not to cater to the "official";
- more frequently incorporate live broadcasts, stand-up specials, on-the-spot phone interviews, breaking news reports, and vox pop into the structure of news blocks;
- skillfully alternate between "hard" and "soft" reporting;
- pay more attention to news packaging, graphic techniques, digital video effects, electronic captions, etc.;
- promote the further development of personalization in news releases and the promotion of reporters and correspondents;
- utilize news promotion effectively.

In the final analysis, it becomes clear that there are no trivial details in the work of news programs. Everything is important here: the layout of the issue, the construction of individual stories within it, the headlines, the introductions, the development of the news story, and its promotion. No less significant, as we have seen, is the thoughtful use of a variety of methods for delivering information to the audience.

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